

WS7a Platform

Data governance for energy planning in Zambia

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1 Introduction

1.1 Aim of this document

This report explores data governance and management in the context of Zambia's Integrated Resource Plan (IRP). It aims to assess and document current data governance and management practices for energy planning, to identify areas for improvement and to evaluate the potential role of a data repository or catalogue to address these gaps as part of a broader reflection on Zambian data governance. The report discusses five key concepts of data governance, explores roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders involved in the energy planning and discusses Zambia's energy planning community. It then explores in detail the data lifecycle of energy data in the country focusing on data sharing, preparation and analysis. The findings demonstrate that while data governance mechanisms are in place, they can be improved through the implementation of a data repository within the data community. In addition to this, incorporating a data officer role within key organizations and throughout data lifecycle processes can further strengthen data management.

1.2 Background

The availability of a reliable, climate-resilient and affordable energy supply is a prerequisite to establishing prosperous and inclusive economic development in Zambia. As with any planning effort, there is a need for high-quality data and data management processes. Appropriate methods for data collection, processing, curation and publication are required to support evidence-based decision-making. The quality of data constrains the quality of insights derived from models that use the data. Thus, high-quality data is a prerequisite for high-quality insights. However, missing data should not cause decision paralysis, and alternatives to expensive manual data collection methods, such as satellite imagery or openly licensed sources such as Open Street Map could supplement or replace traditional approaches to data collection.

Following the publication of the Integrated Resource Plan in 2023, CIG Zambia (CIGZ) was asked by the Zambian Ministry of Energy to design, resource and establish a Centre for Sustainable Energy Modelling (CSEM), to support the development and exploitation of evidence-based decision-making based on empirical data and modelling and use this evidence to unlock financing. The objective of CSEM is to provide high-quality independent technical advice and assistance to Zambian government institutions and private sector organisations. These institutions and organisations aim to harness the potential of Zambia's cities and towns to act as drivers for economic growth and job creation through various projects and programmes.

During 2023, CIG Zambia approached the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) Platform to link to the existing expertise in data governance and open science. CCG is a £100m UK Aid-funded project led

by Loughborough University. The CCG team includes leading experts in practical, applicable research in sustainable development and related topics. CCG is currently active in Kenya, Zambia, Ghana, Vietnam, Lao PDR and India. CCG's strategy is one of partnership, collaboration and empowerment. The CCG Platform, led by the KTH Royal Institute of Technology, works on multiple topics including data governance and open science. CIG Zambia is a multi-year FCDO-funded demand-led project aimed at supporting the Government of the Republic of Zambia in implementing the IRP. The project is being implemented by Cowater International, an international development consultancy headquartered in Canada.

KTH has also participated in the FCDO-funded UK PACT Kenya project, where KTH developed a prototype national data repository for Kenya. The objective of that work was to operate as a neutral broker to investigate the benefits and costs of various alternative technical solutions to data management and sharing between Kenyan data owners and data users. One specific challenge addressed was the need to manage the different data needs for energy planning of the 47 counties in Kenya with those of the national planning unit.

CIG Zambia's request presented a timely opportunity for the CCG Platform team, as this opportunity allows the approach from the Kenyan case to be applied in a similar way to the Zambian context. Some of the lessons learned from Kenya have been reported in Ramirez Rodriguez et al. (2024) focusing on data security and privacy. The following sections summarise and explain key data governance concepts discussed in Ramirez Rodriguez et al. (2024) concerning the Zambian context.

This report covers the work conducted with CIG Zambia since April 2024. Key results in the project included establishing a prototype data repository for Zambia, mapping key stakeholders and data sets, an in-person workshop in Lusaka in December 2024, and the publication of this report.

1.2.1 Legal Framework

The IRP is a long-term strategy to establish a reliable and cost-effective electricity framework in Zambia. It is a 30-year plan extending to 2050, with a strong focus on 2030. It covers demand, generation, transmission, distribution, and off-grid access as well as cross-cutting issues related to climate change, gender and social inclusion (*Integrated Resource Plan for the Power Sector in Zambia, 2023*).

As high-quality data is needed for the development of the IRP, data sharing is envisioned to take place between CSEM and various organizations in Zambia. As stated in Ramirez Rodriguez et al., (2024) "*in the context of energy planning, data sharing refers to the activities where two or more stakeholders exchange information used for energy models, analysis of an energy system or an assessment on gender equality and social inclusion issues connected to, for example, energy access and climate change resilience.*"

These sharing activities are quite influenced by the legal framework of the country. Table 1 summarizes some of the most relevant acts and documents in relation to data sharing, data access and privacy. The legal framework also includes relevant data concepts as presented in Box 1.

Table 1. Legal framework for data sharing in Zambia

<i>Constitution of Zambia, 1996</i>	Article 17 encompasses the right to privacy, although data protection is not explicitly stated (Chisenga & Muzimu, 2024)
<i>THE ELECTRONIC COMMUNICATIONS AND TRANSACTIONS ACT, 2021</i>	Regulates electronic transactions
<i>THE CYBER SECURITY AND CYBER CRIMES ACT, 2021</i>	Regulates interception of communication and publication of personal information
<i>THE DATA PROTECTION ACT, 2021</i>	Regulates the use, protection, collection, sharing, storage and processing of personal data
<i>The Data Protection (Registration and Licensing) Regulations, 2021</i>	Regulates the registration of data controllers and data processors

In Zambia, no specific legislation governs energy data. However, data-sharing activities fall under the Electronic Communications and Transactions Act, as they qualify as data messages under its definition. While the act primarily addresses electronic transactions, such as payments, it remains a relevant consideration in the context of energy data governance.

Moreover, as the IRP addresses cross-cutting issues such as gender, climate change, and social inclusion, it involves the use of personal data, which is governed by the Data Protection Act. While this working paper does not focus on data security, it is important to consider data security protocols that align with the legal framework and use relevant governance mechanisms to address this issues as presented in Ramirez Rodriguez et al. (2024)

Box 1. Data definitions in Zambia

- Data: electronic representation of information in any form (*THE ELECTRONIC COMMUNICATIONS AND TRANSACTIONS ACT, 2021*).
- Data message: data generated, sent, received or stored by electronic, optical or similar means and includes, but is not limited to electronic data interchange (EDI), voice, stored record, electronic mail, mobile

communications audio and video recordings (*THE ELECTRONIC COMMUNICATIONS AND TRANSACTIONS ACT, 2021*).

- Personal data: data which relates to an individual who can be directly or indirectly identified from that data which includes a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier, or one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person (*THE DATA PROTECTION ACT, 2021*).
- Sensitive personal data: personal data which by its nature may be used to suppress the data subject's fundamental rights and freedoms and includes: the race, marital status, ethnic origin or sex; genetic data and biometric data; child abuse data, political opinions, religious beliefs or other beliefs of a similar nature, membership of a trade union, physical or mental health, or physical or mental condition (*THE DATA PROTECTION ACT, 2021*).

1.2.2 Data Governance and governance mechanisms

Building on the approach used in Ramirez Rodriguez et al. (2024) we examined data governance and governance mechanisms within the Zambian context. Data governance refers to “*the exercise of managing data assets through decision-making rights and duties, and the implementation of standards, policies, procedures, roles, and responsibilities within a data community*” (Alhassan et al., 2016; Ladley 2020; Eryurek 2021, as cited in Ramirez Rodriguez et al., 2024).

In the context of energy planning, a data community is understood as “*a group of stakeholders who share a social, economic or professional interest across the data lifecycle to create and manage knowledge resources*” (*African Data Consensus, 2015; Nishikawa, 2020, as cited in Ramirez Rodriguez et al., 2024*). Figure 1 illustrates the data governance framework used by Ramirez Rodriguez et al. (2024) to analyse data-sharing activities in Kenya. This framework provides a basis to examine five data domains in the context of energy planning and will be used to understand the diverse set of practices and mechanisms used for data sharing in Zambia. A detailed description of these domains can be found in Box 2.

Figure 1. Data domains – Data governance framework for energy planning (Ramirez Rodriguez et al., 2024)

Box 2. Data domain definitions (adapted from Ramirez Rodriguez et al., 2024)

- Data principles: Normative, reusable and directive set of statements that describe the basic doctrines of data governance. (Brous et al., 2016; *The TOGAF® Standard, Version 9.2*, n.d.)
- Data Lifecycle: Represent the approach to plan, collect, prepare, analyse, visualize, access, share, use, archive, store and delete data (Abraham et al., 2019; Shah et al., 2021)
- Data quality: Ability of data to satisfy its usage requirements across any stage in its life cycle. (Abraham et al., 2019; Moses et al., 2022)
- Data privacy and security: Preservation of security concerning access, use, processing, and storage controls. (Abraham et al., 2019; Jamul, 2023)
- Data monitoring: Tracking and enforcing conformance with regulatory requirements and organizational policies, standards, procedures, and SLAs. (Abraham et al., 2019)

In the data lifecycle domain, sharing and publishing data involves the exchange of information to benefit stakeholders (Shah et al., 2021). The preparation phase encompasses integrating, filtering, and enriching data, while the analysis phase involves developing data analytics to extract knowledge and uncover new insights (Shah et al., 2021). Our aim was to identify *processes* for these phases, focusing on the procedural governance mechanisms described by Abraham et al. (2019) which consist of “*standardized, documented and repeatable methods used to govern data.*”

Another important mechanism we examined is *roles and responsibilities* which involves “*assigning privileges and tasks to users, groups, public, or other roles*” (Roles, 2024). Ramirez Rodriguez et al., 2024 analyse this mechanism through a diagram that illustrates the data ecosystem and the diverse data communities within it. This approach helps map the different stakeholders’ roles, track the flows of information and to identify the data intermediaries. Figure 2 presents an example of a data ecosystem diagram while box 3 contains the corresponding definitions.

Figure 2. Data ecosystem diagram (Ramirez Rodriguez et al., 2024).

Box 3. Data community definitions (reproduced from Ramirez Rodriguez et al., 2024)

- Data ecosystem: Multiple data communities, all types of data, institutions, laws and policy frameworks and innovative technologies and tools interacting to share information (*African Data Consensus*, 2015)
- Data community: Group of stakeholders who share a social, economic or professional interest across the data lifecycle to create and manage knowledge resources (*African Data Consensus*, 2015; Nishikawa, 2020)
- Data provider: Actor that collects, creates and/or aggregates data, defines data risks and data requirements. (Abraham et al., 2019; Lis & Otto, 2021).
- Data consumer: Actor that uses data for analysis, defines data requirements and monitors data issues (Abraham et al., 2019).
- Data intermediary: Third-party actors who provide specialized resources and capabilities to (i) enhance the supply, flow, and/or use of open data and/or (ii) strengthen the relationships among various open data stakeholders (Massey, 2022)
- Member: Actor that produces and consumes data or participates in the management of data in the data community.

Finally, we intended to establish principles for classifying data to better define processes. This can be achieved using data classification, a mechanism where data is ranked according to the risks associated with it (Bhajararia, 2022, as cited in Ramirez Rodriguez et al. 2024). Data classification can take various forms, such as identifying data as commercially sensitive—meaning it contributes to economic value (Hirth, 2020)—or as personal data, as outlined in Box 1. One example can be found in Ramirez Rodriguez et al. (2024) where they use data classification to suggest sorting data into three different categories in the context of Kenya energy planning.

2 Methods

In section 2.1, we describe the implementation of a prototype data repository in collaboration with CIG Zambia to assess the feasibility of using CKAN as an internal data management tool. CKAN was selected due to its open-source nature, established use in data management, and ability to support metadata management, access control, and API integrations. These features made it a strong candidate for handling datasets in our context. Section 2.2 presents the three different approaches to stakeholder engagement, carried out in person and remotely.

2.1 Data Repository

A data repository can be defined as “*a digital or physical environment where data is stored, organised, managed, accessed and preserved for a period to be used for analytical or reporting purposes*” (as cited in Ramirez Rodriguez et al., 2024). For the management of energy data in Zambia we identified CKAN as the most suitable tool for data management after reviewing CKAN, InvenioRDM, Semantic Media Wiki and Socrata. This review was informed by the World Bank Open Data Toolkit (*Open Data Toolkit | Technology Options | Data*, n.d.).

CKAN is an open-source system that facilitates data management. It allows actors to easily publish, share, catalogue, store and access datasets using a browser-based graphical user interface (*CKAN - The Open-Source Data Management System*, 2024).

The prototype data repository developed for the project is hosted on Microsoft Azure and was planned to be hosted until the end of March 2025, after which it would be decommissioned. The source code for deploying the prototype instance is available on GitHub, (https://github.com/ClimateCompatibleGrowth/ccg_ckan/), and while the prototype is active it is available online at (<http://zambia.swedencentral.cloudapp.azure.com/>). The data repository is hosted in the cloud on Swedish servers, so outside Zambia. As we discuss later, the intention is for the data repository and catalogue to be hosted in Zambia. In the interim period before the Zambian hosting is live, we can continue to host the data repository on Swedish servers, but this prohibits certain types of data from being stored as this could contravene local (Zambian) privacy laws.

During the work, we identified that the data repository would need to be hosted and administered by Smart Zambia. Smart Zambia is a “*Division under the Office of the President mandated to coordinate and implement electronic government (E-Government) for the citizens, businesses and within government for improved service delivery*” (<https://www.szi.gov.zm/>).

2.2 Stakeholder Engagement

Engagement with stakeholders involved four different approaches:

- Documenting initial data management work done by a consultant within CIG Zambia. Details on the results can be found on the GitHub repository: (<https://github.com/ClimateCompatibleGrowth/CIGZambia>).
- Regular meetings from March 2024 and bi-weekly meetings from December 2024 to March 2025. The work involved discussions around data governance, a data mapping exercise and follow-up activities after a workshop. To develop the data mapping, we adapted a template that was originally developed for another project in the Climate Compatible Growth programme to the specific needs of the data mapping exercise.
- Semi-structured interviews aimed to understand data management practices and the use of the data repository. The interview plan can be found in [10.5281/zenodo.15112962](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15112962).
- One workshop held from the 2nd to 5th of December 2024 in Lusaka together with the CIG Zambia team and KTH. Details of the workshop can be found on: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14725707>

3 Results

In section 3.1 we present the results concerning data classification and the types of data used for energy planning in Zambia. In section 3.2 we discuss roles and responsibilities and the data ecosystem in the country. In Section 3.3 and 3.4 we present the results for the data lifecycle focusing on sharing/publishing, preparing and analysing activities. Finally in Section 3.5 we share other relevant results shared during our stakeholder engagement and the implementation of the data repository.

3.1 Data classification: function and purpose

Figure 3 describes datasets used for the Integrated Resource Plan (IRP) using two complementary classification approaches. The first approach, data by function, categorises data based on its role in the energy system, including generation, transmission, distribution, financial data, demand data, and crosscutting data. The second approach, data by purpose, distinguishes between core data, supplementary data, and crosscutting data based on how the information is used. Core data encompasses specific details about generation assets and capacity, information on the status of transmission and distribution infrastructure, electricity consumption figures, and the geographical locations of demand centres. Supplementary data includes information that supports core data or is driven by policy needs. Cross-cutting data encompasses variables related to climate, environment, gender, and various socio-economic factors.

In terms of function, key stakeholders involved in sharing generation data include ZESCO, Independent Power Producers (IPPs), the Copperbelt Energy Corporation (CEC), and regulatory bodies such as the Energy Regulation Board (ERB) and the Rural Electrification Authority (REA). Given Zambia's reliance on hydroelectric power, hydrological data is particularly important and is overseen by organizations such as WARMA, the Zambezi River Authority (ZRA), the Zambia Meteorological Department, and the Worldwide Fund for Nature. Transmission and distribution data is shared by institutions such as ZESCO and ERB, as well as IPPs and CEC. Additionally, REA contributes data specifically related to distribution. Financial data is managed by institutions including the Ministry of Finance and ZESCO.

Future demand data provides insights into electricity consumption patterns across different sectors in the future, including demographics, agriculture, transport, and industry. The Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock provide data on planned and proposed agricultural yields from different crops, while the Ministry of Transport and Logistics, Road Transport and Safety Agency (RTSA) and the Zambia Revenue Authority (ZRA) provide data for rail development and electric vehicles use. The Ministry of Commerce, Trade, and Industry provides data on planned industrial parks and the World Bank, the Zambia Institute for Policy Analysis and Research, and ZESCO provide broader demand data and policy-related data. Prospective new energy customers from CEC and other IPPs,

Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources also have relevant data for geospatial based planning. The Zambia Development Agency (ZDA) includes prospective industrial developments with their expected localities of development which could also be integrated.

Finally, institutions such as the Ministry of Energy (Office for Promoting Private Power Investment), the Worldwide Fund for Nature (WWF), the Zambia Meteorological Department, and the Zambia Statistics Agency are responsible for collecting crosscutting data. In the future, crosscutting data should be divided into more specific subcategories—such as gender, climate, and broader socio-economic factors—to enhance the depth of analysis and tackle any issues with security.

Figure 3. Data types for energy planning in Zambia

3.2 Roles and responsibilities

The results for the analysis of the energy data ecosystem are presented in Figure 4. On the left, one data community consists of organizations that act as data providers including Smart Zambia and Zam Stats and others which supply data to the Ministry of Energy (MoE). Within the members we observe ZESCO, Energy Regulation Board (ERB), Rural Electrification Authority (REA), Indeni Energy Company Zambia (INDENI), Tazama Pipelines Limited (Tazama), Zambia Revenue Authority (ZRA), Industrial Development Corporation (IDC), Office for Promoting Private Power Investment (OPPPI), Line Ministries and Cooperating Partners which supply data to the MoE and to CSEM (in the future) and retrieve data from the MoE. In the centre, we find the Zambian Management Information System (MIS) which sits within the Department of Planning Information (DPI). The MIS was supported by the EU to enhance how data and information is handled within the ministry. Within the MIS sits the MoE's Monitoring and Evaluation coordination office. This office ensures the quality of the programming of the MoE.

On the right, another data community represents the data consumers, which include Parliament, Cabinet, Ministry of Finance and National Planning (MOFNP), other Line Ministries, and the public. Additionally, other stakeholders, conferences, workshops, reports, and publications contain and retrieve data from the energy data community. These actors are presented as a distinct data community as they do not contribute to the management of energy data.

Figure 4. Energy data ecosystem in Zambia

3.3 Data lifecycle: sharing

The data mapping exercise included two distinct results. The first one is a higher-level understanding on data flows and processes focusing on data sharing workflows per organization. The other exercise focuses on a detailed transformation of datasets.

The results from the first exercise are presented in Figure 5 and 6. Figure 5 categorizes organizations based on their data acquisition processes. It consists of three categories: Concise Data Acquisition Processes, Extended Data Acquisition Processes, and Unknown Data Acquisition Processes. Organizations with concise processes, meaning that they follow three to six steps for data acquisition, include ZESCO, REA, Copperbelt Energy Corporation (CEC), ERB, the Association for IPPs, and the World Wildlife Fund for Nature. These entities likely have fewer bureaucratic barriers for obtaining data.

Meanwhile, organizations requiring extended data acquisition processes tend to follow a more structured, multi-step approach. These include several ministries, such as the Ministry of Energy (MOE), Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Transport and Logistics, Ministry of Commerce, Trade, and Industry, Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock, Ministry of Mines and Mineral Development, Ministry of Green Economy and Environment, and the Ministry of Energy (Office for Promoting Private Power Investment), with the last two being highlighted as their processes vary slightly in comparison to the one presented on Figure 6.

Lastly, organizations under the unknown data acquisition category have processes that were not mapped during the duration of the project. These include GETFiT/Globelec, the World Bank, Zambezi River Authority (ZRA), the Chamber of Mines, the Zambia Revenue Authority, the Road Transport and Safety Agency, WARMA, the Zambia Institute for Policy Analysis and Research, the Zambia Statistics Agency, and the Zambia Meteorological Department.

Figure 5. Energy data acquisition per organization in Zambia

Figure 6 presents the data acquisition processes for energy data in Zambia defined as the Extended Data Acquisition Process and the Concise Data Acquisition Process. The extended process follows a hierarchical structure with multiple approval layers, starting from the Requester and progressing through Permanent Secretary, Director, Associate Director, Principal, Senior Officer and the Officer. Once the process ends, the dataset is shared to the requester following the same steps backwards.

In contrast, the concise process is streamlined, involving fewer steps. It begins with the Requester and moves through Approver 1, Approver 2, with placeholders for Approver 3, Approver 4, and Approver 5 indicating that the organizations under the concise data acquisition process have between three to six steps. This second process appears to be a more efficient method for acquiring data.

Figure 6. Energy data acquisition process for energy data in Zambia

Requesting data often requires continuous interaction between the requester and the organizations to clarify data formatting, transformation, and the meaning of the information. Since each organization has its way of working, ongoing discussions are essential for alignment and mutual understanding.

“You know, some particular discussions were needed in order to get the right type of the data. To avoid, let's say, any confusion with the data requirements [...], to specifically explain what we need, why we need it and to clarify if they have any questions about it.” [1]

“People didn't really get to understand certain fields of the data that was requesting for.” [2]

“Sometimes you ask for data, and you get more than what you've requested. And sometimes you ask for data, and you get not anything what you need. Sometimes it's in formats that like you don't really fully understand.” [3]

This issue is caused by a lack of overall data management within each organisation. Our findings showed that data is often shared informally between individuals who create and manage their files without proper documentation on the meaning of the data and how it has been transformed. As a result, knowledge about the dataset remains only with the data owner. While the information may be accessible if the individual remains in the organization, it is often lost when they leave.

“Sometimes it's very difficult to understand who is doing what, who is responsible, for what and basically who is keeping certain pieces of information.” [1]

“I think what really struck me was how much the exercise had been done as individuals from like an individual standpoint and not from an organizational standpoint. So, it was people going around asking for documents, getting documents because they had relationships through people, working on those documents, filing them in there, creating an Excel sheet that didn't really have a lot of explanation to it or underpinning to it, but like made sense to them as they were working through it.” [3]

3.4 Data lifecycle: preparation and analysis

Our initial work with CIG Zambia focused on understanding data management efforts done by a consultant to collate and process generation and demand data which was subsequently used in the Integrated Resource Plan. Figure 7 summarizes the results, classifying the datasets and scripts by activity performed to them. Each activity consists of specific tasks aimed at ensuring proper data management and integration.

Figure 7. Data management activities within CSEM

In the Collate phase, demand and generation data are gathered and prepared for further processing. This could involve adding metadata, standardizing column names, handling date and time formats, and performing data cleaning and transformation. Additionally, data structuring, aggregation, merging, and enrichment take place to ensure consistency and completeness. Summary statistics can also be calculated, and the data is reshaped, consolidated, and stored in a structured format for further use.

The Process phase focuses on performing operations necessary to prepare the data for analysis and integration into a unified system. This includes additional data cleaning, transformation, and preparation for database storage. The data is organized and structured in a way that facilitates analysis and ensures compatibility with the final database. In the case of the combined data, a unified data lake is created for further analysis.

In the Update phase, new data is added to a table. This ensures that the database remains up to date with the latest available information, enabling accurate analysis and decision-making based on the most recent data.

Lastly, the Additional Scripts section includes further data exploration and integration of additional data sources. This involves exploring CIG data and collating information from the Labour Force and Migration Survey (LCMS) data, which may provide further insights or enhance the existing dataset.

Other data transformations performed for the Integrated Resource Plan were explored in the second data mapping exercise, and the results are presented in Figures 8, 9, 10 and 11. Figure 8 depicts the data transformation from the source to its final input in Antares for energy demand. The yellow cylinders represent data sets shared by ZESCO with CIG Zambia. ZESCO devised an hourly demand load profile, which provides the shape of energy demand for every 330kV node in the base year of the analysis, set as 2020 for the IRP. Additionally, ZESCO provided data for annual peak demand per substation (330kV) for 2020, and these are combined to give an annual hourly peak demand by substation. This annual hourly demand is then modified according to econometric load forecasting conducted by a consultant using the sectoral demand split for 2020 also provided by

ZESCO. Alongside assumptions on electricity trade, these elements form a projection for hourly demand for specific future years of 2026, 2030, 2040 and 2050.

Figure 8. Demand mapping for the current IRP

Figure 9 illustrates data flows in relation to generation technology parameters necessary for Antares modelling. On the left side the original datasets are listed along with their respective source. These datasets are obtained from a range of sources, including publicly available global sources such as the World Bank, and Zambia-specific data owners, such as the Ministry of Energy, Zambezi River Authority and ZESCO. Then CIG Zambia will process and transform these datasets to make them suitable for input into Antares. In most cases, these data were extracted from reports or manually transformed in Excel before being integrated into the model.

Figure 9. Generation technology parameters

Several key issues came up during the discussions around the two workflows presented in Figure 8 and 9. One concern was that the data provided by ZESCO is often estimated due to missing data in ZESCO's records. These data gaps arise from various factors, including blackouts that disrupt data collection and human errors in manual data entry. In addition, there was uncertainty regarding ZESCO's ability to record and archive data. This means that data is often unavailable even though it may have been collected.

Unfortunately, even when data does exist, ZESCO is often reluctant to share it due to the reputational issue associated with poor data quality. Due to the lack of data infrastructure within ZESCO, the responsibility for hosting and maintaining data sets often falls on individuals who know they will need the data in the future. Individuals ensure they have the data they need to do their job. However, when individuals leave ZESCO, those datasets leave with them. This situation is undesirable from multiple perspectives, not least security, but also because those that wish to find and access data cannot do so due to the fragmentation of data management within ZESCO.

Figure 10 presents the transmission analysis process, which is divided into two main components: Technical Analysis and Financial Analysis. The Technical Analysis begins with multiple data sources, including peak demand mapping, aggregated generation at 330kV nodes, Existing Transmission Network (ZESCO), and a SAPP pool plan. These datasets undergo data processing to ensure compatibility with Antares, which involves utilising the Power Factory Model and applying post-processing techniques to linearize the model. The outcome of this process is the identification of the final transmission candidate project inclusive of FACT devices for reactive power compensation.

On the Financial Analysis side, the results derived from the technical analysis are used to estimate the cost of the transmission candidate projects. Financial data is then integrated into a financial model, which supports cost evaluation and decision-making.

Figure 10. Transmission

Figure 11 represents the CSEM distribution analysis, which also consists of Technical Analysis and Financial Analysis. In the Technical Analysis section, the process begins with Peak Demand Mapping and Existing Distribution Networks (ZESCO) as key input datasets. These datasets are processed using the Power Factory Model, which identifies and proposes new distribution substations based on the analysis. The Financial Analysis section uses this technical output to estimate the cost of distribution candidate projects.

Figure 11. Distribution

3.5 Reflections on the utility of a data repository and catalogue

During our workshop with CIG Zambia and stakeholders in the energy community, we investigated three potential case applications of the data repository. The first was using the data repository as a catalogue for raw data. In this setting, all primary data sets received from data sources, such as ZESCO, would first be entered into the data repository. The team walked through the process of writing the metadata for an example dataset. The process raised several questions for CSEM, about how to fill in the metadata form fields. The key questions and issues were:

- Who is an “author”?
- Who is a “maintainer”?
- How can we register multiple dataset authors?
- How to ensure that single-word tags are entered to be useful for searching

Another observation from the workshop is related to data formats realizing that they must be managed to make effective use of the CKAN software. The first observation was that Excel workbooks, which have been commonly used in the compilation of the integrated resource plan, are not well suited to the data repository because they do not impose any constraints on how the data is organized. This prevents the automated ingestion of data to CKAN. The second observation was that the preview and interactive visualization features are only operational when you upload data in a long (or narrow or tidy) format, where each row in the file contains one observation per feature or subject.

Another potential use of CKAN is to ensure data remains up to date. Since data is constantly changing and essential for models, external data requesters must frequently obtain the latest versions. However, this process is not well managed at CIG Zambia and could be improved in the future with a dedicated tool.

“So, in my opinion, it's not only about like, providing, some data in the beginning and then completely forgetting to really update the data. It's a matter of like, having the continuous habit to really keep the latest data sets in this tool because simply power system is, is a live thing. It changes, you know, it changes on a monthly or yearly basis.” [1]

“If there is a streamlined way in which data could be requested, and maybe also that to ensure that it's updated frequently. That could be also another area where that is improved.” [2]

4 Recommendations

CIG Zambia identified the need for more effective data management to support the development of the IRP. At a higher level (per organisation), we have observed the absence of a data intermediary to facilitate data exchanges. We propose that the future CSEM takes on this role, driving data management efforts.

Figure 11 presents the proposed data ecosystem. In this simplified model, all member organizations share and access data through the data repository. Smart Zambia acts as the host of the repository, as they already have the necessary infrastructure to do so. While CSEM would also be part of the repository, its primary role would focus on governance—enhancing data flow between organizations. Some of CSEM’s responsibilities would include:

- Documenting key processes, such as data acquisition and repository management (uploading, modifying, and deleting data).
- Defining data quality metrics, security measures, and data principles.
- Establishing data monitoring activities.

Figure 12. Proposed data ecosystem for data sharing in Zambia

Since these responsibilities need to be taken, we also have identified the need for a data officer within each organization to oversee internal data management. This data officer would be responsible for maintaining datasets in the data repository and managing access requests within the organization and ensuring adherence to protocols for lifecycle processes like uploading, changing, deleting, storing and archiving datasets, adherence to metadata template and security

protocols. Additionally, the data officer would be responsible for managing the organization's presence in the CKAN instance.

Other relevant roles within organizations, such as data stewards and data custodians, require further investigation to determine how they fit within the context of energy planning in Zambia.

Finally, it is necessary to define how the repository will be administered between Smart Zambia and CSEM. Key considerations include access control, repository governance, and the development of CKAN components (both front-end and back-end).

When using the repository, data will need to be reformatted before it is entered into it to make full use of the validation and preview functionality provided by CKAN. However, there is still a need to record or archive the original raw files as received from the data providers. The proposal is that data ingested to CSEM follows a process as described in the Figure 13.

Figure 13. Proposed process for uploading data

The process begins at stage 1 when a new data asset is received from a data source. The data analyst should first check that the data is correctly formatted for CKAN. If the file is an Excel workbook, this means ensuring that each sheet contains only tables of data, only one table per sheet and that there is no white space at the top of the sheet. The first row should contain the table headers. To make the best use of the CKAN preview and visualization tools, the data should also be presented in tidy (or long) format. If the data is in a different format, for example, a PDF file, then no reformatting is required. If the data is a CSV file, then there may be a need to convert the file to tidy format, which would require the use of a script. In stage 3, the data analysis should archive the file, exactly as received from the data provider, complete with all the relevant metadata into the CKAN data

repository. After the file has been archived, stage 4, in which the data is reformatted can take place, with a second dataset created. The `source` field of the dataset can reference the original, unformatted dataset created in stage 3.

Once the metadata has been written and the file uploaded, the automated process of ingesting the uploaded data to the CKAN Datastore begins. This is performed automatically using a software called XLoader in the background. During this process, the data is parsed, data types are detected, and the data is loaded line by line into the Datastore. This allows the data to be searched via the API and previewed via the web front-end. If the ingest is successful, the data analyst can proceed to prepare views for the data, including interactive visualisations. The final step is to perform quality checks in stage 7. The data is now ingested, published and ready for consumption based on the visibility settings set during the dataset creation phase (public or private).

5 Conclusion

In this report, we have outlined the main results of the collaboration between CIG Zambia and the CCG Platform from April 2024 to March 2025. Together, we have explored how data management practices can be implemented by the to-be-created Centre for Sustainable Energy Modelling and supplemented by an open-source digital tool, CKAN, which enables the cataloguing and deposit of datasets.

The data for the Integrated Resource Plan were categorised into generation, transmission, distribution, financial data and demand – disaggregated into agricultural, transport, industrial, mining and other, and cross-cutting. For each of these data categories, several data owners were identified, each of which has different roles and responsibilities relating to data, and to each other. We highlighted that data sharing differed across data owners. ZESCO, REA, CEC, ERB and the Association for IPPs use a shorter process for approving data requests, whereas the various government ministries use an extended process which requires up to seven levels of approval. There is still work to be done to better understand the processes at other organisations.

For the future Centre for Sustainable Energy and Modelling, the key insight from this data mapping work is that it is a huge effort to manage the large numbers of stakeholders and individual requests for data necessary to complete an Integrated Resource Plan. This was recognised at the beginning of this work, but we have now clarified the magnitude of the effort required, and we can now recommend strategies to manage this complexity.

We also explored and documented the existing data sets and analysis conducted by a consultant for the integrated resource plan. This documentation can act as a template, for how this type of analysis can be made more repeatable and understandable. In general, much of the work required for compiling the integrated resource plan will follow an extract/transform/filter workflow, combining the datasets so that they are in the correct format and structure required by the

modelling inputs. The flow diagrams developed in the workshop with the CIG Zambia team that developed in the Integrated Resource Plan further clarified the steps involved in transforming data from sources for the modelling work. We also showed how the CKAN data catalogue could be integrated into this workflow to ensure that data is catalogued as soon as it is received from a data owner. The process of cataloguing includes documenting the process of requesting the dataset, including details of the individual contact at the data owner organisation.

Furthermore, we propose that the future Centre for Sustainable Energy Modelling can play a key role in enabling a transition to more sustainable data management practices across government institutions and parastatals. CSEM is unique in that it requires data from so many other bodies and this presents an opportunity to share knowledge and innovate new processes as it interacts with these different entities. Specifically, CSEM could act as a data intermediary, providing a valuable service by publishing the CKAN data catalogue, not necessarily of the data itself, but of the metadata, enabling others to find and access the data they need.

Finally, we identified the need for a counterpart at CIG Zambia who could focus on the technical management of data and support the modelling and analysts who focus on their energy domain expertise. During this time, CIG Zambia recruited a data officer who will continue to support the team as we move towards implementing a national data repository for the Centre for Sustainable Energy Modelling.

In terms of the next steps, we are investigating promising developments with the Department for Planning Information in the Ministry of Energy and with Smart Zambia, which could provide a natural national host for the CKAN data repository.

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6 Annex – Description of data providers

Not all the following data providers listed are included in the analysis in the report.

Ministry of Energy (MOE)	High-level national energy planning. The ministry is committed to creating a centralised energy database to have all energy data in one place
Copperbelt Energy Corporation (CEC)	The second-largest utility after ZESCO, CEC is a Zambian incorporated power transmission, generation and distribution company. They are able to provide disaggregated statistics of electricity demand for all the mining firms on the Copperbelt Province.

Association for Power Companies	<p>IPPs are entities or companies that generate electricity independently of government-owned utilities or public electricity providers. They are private sector companies that develop, own, and operate power generation facilities, often for the purpose of selling electricity to the grid or directly to consumers. The technology portfolio under IPPs is varied, and the primary off-taker is ZESCO. While a large portion of information on IPP generation can be retrieved through ZESCO and ERB, there is need to collect detailed plant level performance statistics and characteristics.</p>
Ministry of Green Economy and Environment	<p>Under this ministry, the Department of Meteorological Services is the custodian of weather and climate data. This data is particularly critical in the analysis and predication of climate events and the tracing of long-term climate change trends. As stands, aggregate data from the MoGEE is not easily accessible.</p>
Rural Electrification Authority (REA)	<p>REA is responsible for the delivery of electricity to rural areas of Zambia, with the objective of increasing electrification in rural areas and reaching universal access by 2030. REAs mandate is to provide electricity infrastructure to all rural areas using appropriate technologies in order to increase access, productivity and contribute to improved quality of life. They collect quality and pointed statistics of the electricity consumption patterns in Zambia’s rural areas and work closely with ZESCO. However, the detailed asset level performance statistics and characteristics are not currently collected, and would be beneficial in the context of the IRP analysis.</p>
Energy Regulation Board (ERB)	<p>ERB is the regulatory agency for the energy sector in Zambia. It was established to regulate undertakings/utilities in the energy sector including Electricity, Fossil Fuels and Other Forms of Energy such as solar and coal, through specialised licences it would issue. It regulates utilities, including ZESCO and CEC and collects data and information from all licensed electricity generators and service providers. Aggregated data is published in either .pdf, csv/spreadsheet or both formats.</p>

World Bank	The World Bank's Least-Cost Geospatial Electrification Plan provides a geospatial analysis to identify least-cost electrification options for Zambia to reach universal electrification of at minimum Tier 1 by 2030 through a combination of grid densification, grid extension, and mini-grids. The connectivity requirements and investments for the Off Grid sector have been defined through the LCGEP.
Zambezi River Authority (ZRA)	The ZRA collects data and monitors river-flows and meter readings of the Zambezi River basin. This information is critical for climate-reflective energy planning purposes, seeing Zambia historical reliance on hydro-sources.
Zambia Statistics Agency (ZamStats)	ZamStats are the governmental custodians of official statistics in Zambia, including demographic, social and economic data. The collected data is relevant for cross-cutting areas of energy planning, especially in relation to social inclusion, human development and economic empowerment. However, as stands, many of the metrics that would be needed to effectively monitor progress in those areas are not being collected.
ZESCO	Zambia's largest utility is a primary generator of energy sector data. They are also a preferred off-taker for electricity generated by Independent Power Producers (IPPs). Therefore, ZESCO have access to the generation data and profiles for most of the IPPs operating in Zambia
Ministry of Energy (Office for Promoting Private Power Investments)	the OPPPI coordinates feasibility studies for a combined capacity in excess of 2000MW, with some of the projects currently at the stage of PowerPurchase Agreement (PPA) negotiations.
Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock	supporting industries by the production of the required raw materials , producing exportable agricultural goods, generating employment particularly in rural areas, as well as providing food stuffs essential for the sustenance of acceptable nutrition standards and levels.
Ministry of Transport and logistics	Charged with the responsibility to formulate and administer policies and strategies in the transport and logistics sector

Ministry of Commerce, Trade and Industry	Zambia's principal Government body responsible for administering National Policy for Private Sector Development. It coordinates Industrial, Commercial and Trade matters.
Chamber of Mines	Responsible for advancing the interests of its members, local communities, the country and its stakeholders whilst promoting sustainable and responsible mining.
World Wide Fund for Nature	Supports conservation of natural resources in Zambia. WWF is involved in various conservation activities to conserve Zambia's biodiversity upon which the nation's economy and livelihoods largely depend.
Zambia Revenue Authority	Government agency responsible for tax administration in Zambia
Road Transport and Safety Agency	Government agency that regulates and manages road transport and safety in Zambia
Zambia Metrological Department	produce and disseminate weather and climatic information to the aviation, agriculture and other sectors in order to facilitate informed decision making.
WARMA	A semi-autonomous government body mandated to regulate, manage, develop, protect and conserve water resources in the country
GETFit	Project under the Ministry of Energy responsible for the development of 120MW solar projects and 100MW mini hydro power project. Further provide information on the Open Access/Independent System Market Operator
Zambia Institute for Policy Analysis and Research	conduct research and policy analysis that informs public policy. The Institute provides evidence-based policy advice to support Government, the private sector, civil society organisations and other stakeholders.
Ministry of Finance	Responsible for allocation of government funds
Ministry of Mines and	responsible for the development and management of mineral resources in a sustainable manner

Mineral Development	
Industrial Development Company	
Smart Zambia	